
UTBK-SNBT Training and Information Provision for High School and Equivalent Students in Pekalongan

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Received: November 2023 Approved: December 2023 Published: January 2024	Currently, the need for access to public tertiary institutions is important for high school students of the same level in Indonesia, including Pekalongan. Thus, the background of this service activity is carried out primarily to provide more detailed information related to the state university selection process in the form of test-based national selection (SNBP) - computer-based written exam (UTBK), as well as providing practice in the form of entrance exam questions. so that activity participants can better prepare themselves to take part in the selection. This is because, through state universities, high school/equivalent school students will get the opportunity to get quality education. Service activities are carried out using the main method of socialization and assistance in accessing information for state universities by collaborating with service partners from partners, in this case the tutoring party. From the service activities, it was found that the participants were enthusiastic in taking part in the activities as evidenced by good responses during the activities. Information and practice questions are provided so that participants can prepare themselves well for the state university entrance exam.
Keywords: Training, Information Provision, State Universities	

INTRODUCTION

Education has an important role in the life of a nation, whether a nation is advanced or not is influenced by the quality of the nation's education itself. Therefore, the government is trying to improve the quality of human resources through education. Education itself is a "system" for turning a nation and state into a great nation and state as stated in Law no. 20 of 2003 Chapter II article 3 concerning the Indonesian National Education System. In this law, it is emphasized that national education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the life of the nation, aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and a democratic and responsible citizen. In Indonesian, the term education comes from the word "didik" by giving it the prefix "pe" and the suffix "an", meaning "action" (thing, method or so on). The term education originally comes from the Greek "paedagogie", which means guidance given to children. This term was then translated into English as "education" which means development or guidance (Prayogi & Nasrullah, 2023).

Education in general is a conscious and directed effort to help someone support their level and dignity by optimizing and advancing their ability to do all

things well (Mustoip, 2018). It is through education that a person will be able to improve their skills as a result of applying knowledge and experience during the educational process (Yusuf, 2018). Improving the quality of human resources can especially be done when someone takes the formal education route to university. In this case, universities are educational units providing higher education which are obliged to take part in the formation of national character. Higher education educators are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology and art through education, research and community service (Tridharma of Higher Education). Professional higher education teaching staff have the function of teachers, educators and trainers so that they can develop the cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects of students. This is the entry point for character education to be implemented at the tertiary level in Indonesia.

Character development is very important for universities and their stakeholders to become a basis for implementing character education in universities (Widodo, Riadi, & Ardi, 2017). Among the various forms of providing education in higher education, there are universities - in various forms, which are managed by the government and the private sector. In relation to government-managed universities, in this case there are two categories, namely general PTNs which are under the Ministry of Education and Culture and Research and Technology and Religious PTNs which are under the Ministry of Religion (Prayogi, 2022).

In accepting new students, there is a selection that must be followed, with a series of strict tests to obtain (potential) students with the appropriate qualifications and abilities. There are 3 entry routes to PTN in 2023, namely the National Selection Based on Achievement (SNBP), the National Selection Based on Test (SNBT), and the Independent Selection route. SNBP and SNBT are fully prepared by the SNPMB Team, while the Independent Selection route is fully managed by the respective PTN. The reason SNBP and SNBT are handled by the SNPMB Team is for the sake of justice and equality for every SMA/SMK/MA student to enter PTN. In this context, this service activity is carried out, especially with the aim of ensuring that participants have sufficient knowledge and information to access all information related to state universities. This is because the main problem generally faced by service partners is the lack of socialization of various information related to PTN entrance selection material, starting from registration information and especially information related to test forms. This lack of information can have an impact on the low participation rate of high school/equivalent students in accessing education at state universities. Thus, this service activity is directed at familiarizing and improving participants' abilities to face state university entrance exams in the form of practice (try out) in answering the questions given. It is hoped that the implementation of community service in the form of training in answering questions can make participants more enthusiastic and have high spirits in order to get good results later.

METHOD

This community service program is carried out in collaboration with partners from the Pekalongan Neutron Tutoring Institute. This activity is aimed at students of

classes X, XI and XII High School/Equivalent which was held in the Hall of SMAN 1 Kedungwuni Pekalongan on November 12 2023. This service activity took several forms, including;

Socialization

This service activity began by establishing collaboration between the Service Team and the Pekalongan Neutron Tutoring Institute. This socialization was carried out to provide knowledge and understanding of various information related to State Universities which will start opening registration in February-April 2024 so that it is hoped that many high school/equivalent alumni will be able to continue their studies at state universities.

Accompaniment and Providing Motivation

Accompaniment and providing motivation activities are aimed at providing material and information related to state universities. Some information was conveyed such as registration information, registration procedures, forms of entrance tests and matters related to technical procedures for accessing related information and included efforts to provide motivation to continue their education as high as possible as part of efforts to build the nation and state.

Training/Try Out

Training or in this case a try out is aimed at training students' abilities in working on state university entrance exam questions in the form of SNBT-UTBK. Practice questions are prepared in advance by the team and partners with different materials to train participants' abilities in working on questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socialization of Activities

This community service activity begins with program outreach from the service team and partners to discuss plans for program activities to be implemented and coordination with SMAN 1 Kedungwuni Pekalongan regarding the application for permission to use the hall for carrying out activities. Also discussed were efforts to publicize the activity to attract as many participants as possible to take part in this activity.

Accompaniment and Providing Motivation

The briefing and motivation activities are aimed at providing participants with an overview of material and information related to state universities such as registration information, registration procedures, forms of entrance tests and matters related to technical procedures for accessing information related to state universities. Apart from that, motivation is also given to build a mindset about the importance of getting the highest possible education to improve the quality of life and build a better national civilization. Motivation needs to be provided to arouse participants' enthusiasm and desire to continue their education to college. Motivation is emphasized on the greater opportunities that will be obtained if participants receive higher education, especially state education.

After delivering the motivation, several important pieces of information related to information on state universities presented in this activity, especially the PTN entrance pathway in 2024, which consists of three pathways, namely SNBP,

SNBT-UTBK, and SM. First, SNBP is an invitation route to replace the National Selection for State University Entrance (SNMPTN). Students who can take part in SNBP or are eligible students are students selected by the school based on academic and non-academic achievement assessments. It is estimated that SNBP registration can be done in February. Second, SNBT is a National Selection Based on Tests conducted via the Computer-Based Written Examination (UTBK). SNBT is a replacement for the Joint State University Entrance Selection (SBMPTN). The questions in this selection will focus on students' reasoning abilities and not memorization. It is estimated that SNBT registration can be done from March to April. In the 2024 SNBT-UTBK implementation, students will only face questions that focus on understanding and reasoning. There are two main components in the implementation of SNBT -UTBK, namely the Scholastic Potential Test and the Literacy Test. If added together, the total number of questions for the two components is 155 items and is divided into several subtests. Third, SM is an abbreviation for PTN Independent Selection. This route is intended for participants who have not been lucky in SNBP or SNBT. SM is expected to open from May to August depending on each PTN being targeted.

Figure 1. Socialization and Information Provision Activities

Training

The training is carried out with a learning assistance approach for participants who wish to continue their studies at state universities. This training was attended by 382 participants from various schools in various former Pekalongan residency areas. The training is aimed at training students' abilities in working on SNBT-UTBK questions as preparation for entering state universities. SNBT-UTBK practice questions are prepared with a variety of material to train participants' abilities in working on exam questions. In this training activity, a try out of the SNBT-UTBK exam questions was held as well as a discussion. Through this activity, it is hoped that activity participants will be able to increase their academic potential by getting used to working on SNBT-UTBK practice questions as a reference for facing selection to enter state universities. Try out discussions were also provided by the service team with partners so that the participants better understand and master problem solving from the SNBT-UTBK practice questions and are able to hone the participants to think critically, quickly and precisely.

This community service activity was carried out thanks to cooperation and collaboration between all parties involved, namely the service team and activity partner groups. Both partners reciprocally provide support in the implementation of activities, and hope for the sustainability of this program to increase the interest of high school students and the equivalent in continuing their education to tertiary institutions in general. In general, the contribution and participation of participants in taking part in this activity looks enthusiastic and they get many benefits which are also related to future planning and life motivation towards a better life than the current conditions, especially after being given provision and motivation material as well as trying out SNBT-UTBK practice questions.

Figure 2. Training and Try Out on SNBT-UTBK Questions

CONCLUSION

Several conclusions can be drawn from this service activity, including, first, this service activity was carried out as an effort to provide broad information to high school and equivalent students in the former Pekalongan residency area to be able to access information related to state universities. This is because in state universities there are several things that need to be understood specifically, especially related to technical information and practice/familiarity in dealing with the questions being tested. Second, this service activity collaborates with tutoring parties who act as facilitators in efforts to discuss questions on the college entrance exam, especially SNBT-UTBK, so that participants get used to it and can improve their abilities in answering the questions that will be tested later. Third, by taking the format of training and providing information, this service activity succeeded in attracting activity participants to take part in the activity as evidenced by their presence at the activity location. Not only that, this service activity also provided good and memorable results for the participants as evidenced by the enthusiasm of the participants during the activity.

THANK-YOU NOTE

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